

Case Report of Acromegaly Secondary to Pituitary Macroadenoma

Sandra Ivette López Aguilar¹, Luis Daniel Solorzano Espinosa², David Sebastián Ramírez Calvillo³, Oscar Rame Montiel⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Internal Medicine, General Hospital Zone #50, San Luis Potosí. Mexican Social Security Institute, Mexico

ABSTRACT

Acromegaly is a rare endocrine disorder resulting from chronic excess secretion of growth hormone (GH), usually caused by pituitary adenomas. This condition leads to elevated levels of insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF-1), resulting in characteristic somatic and metabolic complications.

We report the case of a 46-year-old female patient with a long-standing history of type 2 diabetes mellitus, who presented with clinical signs suggestive of acromegaly, including prognathism, macroglossia, and enlargement of hands and feet. Laboratory evaluation revealed elevated serum GH and IGF-1 levels, with unsuppressed GH after oral glucose tolerance test. Cranial imaging demonstrated a solid pituitary macroadenoma compressing the optic chiasm. The patient was scheduled for transsphenoidal resection as the first-line treatment.

Discussion:

This case highlights the importance of early clinical suspicion and diagnostic confirmation using ACROSCORE, hormonal evaluation, and imaging. Management decisions were guided by tumor size, biochemical activity, and current clinical guidelines. Multidisciplinary follow-up is essential to assess for remission, monitor comorbidities, and reduce long-term mortality risk.

Conclusion

This report underscores the relevance of timely diagnosis and personalized management in acromegaly. Surgical resection remains the cornerstone of treatment in resectable macroadenomas, with medical therapy reserved for persistent or recurrent disease.

KEYWORDS: Acromegaly, Pituitary macroadenoma, Growth hormone, IGF-1, Transsphenoidal surgery, Case report

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
11 July 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

INTRODUCTION

Acromegaly is a rare disorder caused by chronic hypersecretion of growth hormone (GH). Excess GH stimulates hepatic production of insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF-1), which mediates many of the clinical features of the disease. In 98% of cases, acromegaly is due to GH-secreting pituitary tumors, most commonly macroadenomas (defined as lesions >10 mm), often with sellar or suprasellar extension. Prolactin co-secretion occurs in approximately 25–30% of these tumors. The development of GH-secreting adenomas has been associated with multiple oncogenes and growth factors. One key mutation involves the Gsp oncogene (G-stimulatory protein α subunit gene, **Gs α**). When mutated, the Gs α protein becomes constitutively active, leading to persistent cyclic AMP (cAMP) overproduction and

continuous stimulation of GH release by somatotroph cells. This mutation is found in approximately 30% of GH-secreting tumors. In rare cases, GH hypersecretion originates from extrapituitary sources. These include ectopic pituitary tissue located in areas such as the sphenoid or parapharyngeal sinuses, or GH-producing extrapituitary tumors. Excessive secretion of growth hormone-releasing hormone (GH-RH) from eutopic hypothalamic tumors such as gangliocytomas, hamartomas, or choristomas can also lead to secondary pituitary hyperplasia. Additionally, ectopic GH or GH-RH secretion has been linked to paraneoplastic syndromes associated with tumors such as pancreatic islet cell tumors, bronchial, intestinal, or thymic carcinoids, pheochromocytomas, small cell lung carcinomas, medullary thyroid carcinoma, and adrenal adenomas. Genetic causes of

Case Report of Acromegaly Secondary to Pituitary Macroadenoma

acromegaly include both germline and somatic mutations that affect intracellular signaling pathways in somatotroph tumors. Familial forms of acromegaly may be associated with syndromes such as multiple endocrine neoplasia type 1 (MEN1) and Carney complex, which includes lentiginosis, isolated familial pituitary tumors, adrenal pigmented hyperplasia, testicular tumors, cardiac myxomas, and schwannomas. Mutations in the **X-linked acrogigantism (XLAG)** gene lead to early onset gigantism and are associated with microduplications at Xq26.3, causing overexpression of a mutated form of the GPR101 receptor (a G protein-coupled receptor), which drives GH hypersecretion. Germline mutations in the **AIP** (aryl hydrocarbon receptor-interacting protein) gene are present in up to 30% of patients with familial acromegaly, typically associated with aggressive macroadenomas. The clinical manifestations of acromegaly include enlargement of the hands, feet, jaw, and nose, as well as skin thickening. These features are attributed to the anabolic effects of IGF-1, which

promotes fibroblast proliferation and the synthesis of collagen and glycosaminoglycans.

CASE REPORT

This is a 46-year-old patient with a 15-year history of type 2 diabetes mellitus. She was referred to our district hospital for clinical signs of acromegaly: prognathism, macroglossia, with enlarged hands and feet. For the past 20 years, she has denied galactorrhea, bitemporal hemianopia, or headache. Physical examination revealed acanthosis nigricans, rough skin with a tendency toward seborrheic dermatitis, and areas of parietal alopecia. Visual acuity in the right and left eyeballs was 20/50, macroglossia was present, and a deep voice was present. Prognathism was also present. The patient was otherwise unremarkable. GH and IGF-1 were tested, with a 75-gram glucose stimulation test, with positive results. These tests, combined with hormones, indicated an intact hypothalamic-hypothalamic axis. A simple axial and sagittal cranial CT scan revealed a macroadenoma (Figures 1, 2) and Table 1

Figure 1: Presence of prognathism, facial thickening.

Figure 2: Solid suprasellar tumor measuring 10 x 15 x 15 cm that compresses the optic chiasm.

Case Report of Acromegaly Secondary to Pituitary Macroadenoma

Table 1: Baseline Laboratory and Hormonal Profile of the Patient.

Parameter	Worth	Unit	Reference value / Comment
Glucose (GLU)	253	mg/dL	High (hyperglycemia)
Creatinine (Cr)	0.4	mg/dL	Slightly low, possible low muscle mass or overhydration
Urea	25	mg/dL	Within the normal range
BUN	12	mg/dL	Normal
HbA1c	11.4	%	Very high; chronic poor glycemic control
Chlorine (Cl)	107	mEq/L	Normal
Potassium (K)	4.4	mEq/L	Normal
Sodium (Na)	139	mEq/L	Normal
LH (Luteinizing Hormone)	0.39	mIU/mL	Decreased
Prolactin (PRL)	61.7	ng/mL	High
Estradiol (E2)	47	pg/mL	It depends on the sex and phase of the menstrual cycle / Age
Cortisol	9.27	µg/dL	Normal Morning.
FSH (Follicle Stimulating Hormone)	1.14	mIU/mL	Decreased
GH (Growth Hormone)	14.4	ng/mL	High
IGF-1 (Insulin-like growth factor 1)	494.1	ng/mL	High (VN: 60-350)
IGF-1 index	1.4	—	Slightly elevated (expected value ≤1.0)
75g glucose suppression test	GH > 2.0	ng/mL	Does not suppress, diagnosis of acromegaly if GH >1 ng/mL

DISCUSSION

In the diagnostic approach to acromegaly, the use of a clinical tool known as ACROSCORE (score >2) is recommended to justify measuring IGF-1 levels. Initial biochemical assessment should include basal GH levels (>1 µg/L), IGF-1 levels >1.2 times the upper limit of normal (ULN), and failure to suppress GH to <1 ng/mL following an oral glucose load of 75 grams. Imaging studies, particularly pituitary MRI, are essential to evaluate the presence of adenomas. In this case, the patient was diagnosed with acromegaly secondary to a growth hormone (GH)-secreting pituitary macroadenoma and was scheduled for transsphenoidal resection, which is the first-line treatment, provided the tumor is surgically accessible. The therapeutic strategy for acromegaly should be individualized, considering both tumor characteristics and biochemical activity. Surgical resection was indicated in this case due to the presence of a resectable macroadenoma, with the goal of achieving biochemical remission, defined as GH levels <1 ng/mL and IGF-1 levels within the normal range which correlates with reduced comorbidity risk and normalization of life expectancy [1–5]. If biochemical remission is not achieved or the disease recurs after surgery, adjuvant medical therapy is warranted. This includes somatostatin analogs (octreotide, lanreotide, pasireotide), dopamine agonists (e.g., cabergoline, particularly in mixed GH/PRL-secreting tumors), and pegvisomant, a GH receptor antagonist effective in normalizing IGF-1 in resistant cases. Treatment selection depends on factors such as biochemical response, residual tumor size, side effect profiles, and treatment availability. Baseline GH levels >10 µg/L are associated with an increased risk of persistent disease after surgery. Overall mortality in acromegaly is approximately 60%, primarily due to cardiovascular complications.

Hypertension occurs in 20–60% of patients, often resulting from concentric left ventricular hypertrophy. Other common comorbidities include type 2 diabetes mellitus (30%), obstructive sleep apnea (up to 80%), acromegalic arthropathy, carpal tunnel syndrome, and colorectal polyps (25–30%), with a 2–3 fold increased risk of adenomas and carcinoma compared to the general population. Multidisciplinary follow-up is essential for monitoring hormonal control, residual tumor progression, and comorbidities (cardiovascular, metabolic, and neoplastic), which collectively influence long-term prognosis.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

FINANCING

There was no funding for this work.

REFERENCES

- Abreu-Rosario, C., Cadena-Obando, D., Vergara-López, A., Espinosa de los Monteros-Sánchez, A. L., Portocarrero-Ortiz, L., Gómez Romero, P., Pérez-Guzmán, M. C., Cuevas-Ramos, D., Reza-Albarrán, A. A., González-Virla, B., Sosa-Erosa, E., Rangel-Sánchez, G., Balderrama-Soto, A., Vidrio-Velázquez, M., Pérez-Castañeda, C., Rivera-Hernández, A. de J., Barrientos-Ávalos, J. R., Mora-Hernández, S., Ibarra-Salce, R., & Mercado, M. (2021). Tercer consenso nacional de acromegalia: Recomendaciones para su diagnóstico, tratamiento y seguimiento. *Revista Mexicana de Endocrinología, Metabolismo y Nutrición*, 8(91).

Case Report of Acromegaly Secondary to Pituitary Macroadenoma

- <https://doi.org/10.24875/rme.m21000007>
- II. Beuschlein, F., Strasburger, C. J., Siegerstetter, V., Moradpour, D., Lichter, P., Bidlingmaier, M., Blum, H. E., & Reincke, M. (2000). Acromegaly caused by secretion of growth hormone by non-Hodgkin's lymphoma. *New England Journal of Medicine*, *342*(25), 1871–1876.
<https://doi.org/10.1056/nejm200006223422504>
- III. Colao, A., Grasso, L. F. S., Giustina, A., Melmed, S., Chanson, P., Pereira, A. M., & Pivonello, R. (2019). Acromegaly. *Nature Reviews Disease Primers*, *5*(1), 1–17.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41572-019-0071-6>
- IV. Weinreb, J., & Arora, S. (2023). Acromegaly. *New England Journal of Medicine*, *388*(1), 70–70.
<https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmicm2205570>
- V. Giustina, A., Biermasz, N. R., Casanueva, F. F., Fleseriu, M., Mortini, P., Strasburger, C. J., Wass, J. A. H., Melmed, S., Banfi, G., Barkan, A. L., Beckers, A., Bidlingmaier, M., Brue, T., Buchfelder, M., Chanson, P., Chiloiro, S., Colao, A., & Coopmans, E. C. (2023). Consensus on criteria for acromegaly diagnosis and remission. *Pituitary*.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11102-023-01360-1>